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Three Dimensional Analysis of Shape Rolling Using a Generalized Upper Bound Approach

Abrinia, K. and Fazlirad, A.

Department of Mechanical Engineering, University College of Engineering, University of Tehran, I.R. Iran, P.O. Box 11365-4563, Tel: ++98 912 115 9113, Fax: ++98 21

88013029

Corresponding Author Email: [cabrinia@ut.ac.ir](mailto:cabrina@ut.ac.ir)

Abstract

A generalized analytical method has been proposed to study deformation and calculate pressure and torque for the process of rolling shaped sections. The proposed method is based on the upper bound analysis. To determine kinematically-admissible velocity fields, flow lines have been mathematically formulated using the parameterization of curves. Based on the calculated velocity fields, an upper bound has been found on rolling power. The calculated power has been minimized with respect to unknown variables to yield the value closest to the actual power required.

The proposed general method has been applied to certain rolling passes including square to oval and round to oval. Velocity fields and power relations have been obtained for each process. Computer analysis has been carried out for the mentioned passes using dimensions and conditions from experiments conducted by other workers. Deformation, average roll torque and average rolling pressure results from the analysis have been compared with analytical solutions, numerical analyses and experimental data presented by other workers. It was concluded that the present method gave very good results and was quicker and easier to use.

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Keywords: Shape Rolling, Upper Bound, Roll Pass, Velocity Field, Shaped Sections

Introduction

The primary purpose in analyzing metal forming operations is to determine unknown process variables in order to decide the best design of die/work piece to achieve optimum results. In the case of shape rolling, the purpose becomes optimum design of rolls and the roll pass sequence.

However, as shape rolling operations involve large numbers of process variables and include a complex three dimensional material flow, the design of pass sequences and the prediction of roll load and torque, entry and exit velocities have mostly been based on empirical formulae developed for most conventional materials and rolling conditions [1, 2].

Still, as new shapes and materials are introduced to the rolling industry, development of empirical solutions for roll pass sequences as well as other process parameters requires extensive experiments.

As a result, development of an analytical, theoretical based method to analyze metal flow, roll torque, roll pressure and force and exit velocity for the rolling of shaped sections becomes extremely attractive.

This study attempts to present such a method for the analysis of rolling operations which involve simple geometrical shapes such as squares, ovals, rounds, etc. The analysis uses the upper bound solution, assumes the material rolled is rigid, perfectly plastic, and does not consider combined thermo-mechanical effects. Strain rates and velocities are derived from the parametric definition of streamlines in the deformation zone. Solutions are applied to the square to oval and round to oval rolling operations.

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Previous Work

The first numerical approach to the three-dimensional plastic deformation of rolling was to investigate side spread in flat rolling. Oh and Kobayashi [3] conducted the pioneering study in this field by applying an extremum principle for rigid, perfectly plastic materials combined with numerical analysis. Since then, several other researchers have used three dimensional finite element methods for analyzing spread in rolling [4,5]. Park and Oh developed a rigid-plastic 3D FEM code for the analysis of shape rolling processes, which is capable of handling arbitrary cross-sections [6]. Mori and Osakada [7,8] developed a rigid-plastic 3D FEM to simulate steady-state deformation in shape rolling with grooved rolls. Kim and Altan combined the two-dimensional rigid-plastic finite element method with the slab method to reduce the amount of computation without losing accuracy [9]. Saito et al proposed an upper bound method that was capable of predicting lateral spread, elongation and thickness in flat, concave (diamond) and convex (box) passes [10]. Bayoumi used a flow-line field solution to analyze material flow and stresses in the steady-state rolling of round-oval-round rolling sequence [11]. Komori proposed a new analytical method in which the functional of the large region is minimized and the shape of the large region is updated. This method saved computer memory capacity but required long computational times [12]. Hsiang, Lin developed a piece-wise complex model combining the slab and finite element methods. They divided the deformation zone into several slabs and used FEM to calculate sequentially the velocity field, metal flow, stress and strain distribution for each slab [13]. Kennedy developed an upper bound method for the analysis of metal deformation and stresses in shape rolling of geometrical

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profiles without protrusions [14] based on the general velocity fields proposed by Hill [15].

Method of Analysis

The method proposed in the present study is based on the upper bound method of analysis [16]. The first step in applying the upper bound method is the identification of kinematically-admissible velocity fields through an assumption of the shape of the streamlines in the deformation zone. Based on this velocity field, the total power dissipation for the metal forming process is calculated. Since this predicted power is inherently higher than the actual value required for the process, the shape of streamlines and metal flow distribution can be determined by minimizing the power dissipation with respect to unknown variables of the velocity field.

Fig. 1 shows a quarter of the deformation zone considered for the shape rolling of an arbitrary section to another arbitrary section.

Figure 1 – A quarter of the deformation zone assumed for the rolling of an arbitrary shape to another

The geometrical configuration shown in Fig. 1 is based on the choice of a streamline BB' and a stream surface $OAA'O'$. The entry and exit sections are bound by planes represented by OCD and $OC'D'$ respectively. To simplify relations, a left-hand coordinate system has been employed. It has been assumed that the deformation zone consists of such stream surfaces as $OAA'O'$ within which streamlines such as BB' are located. It has been further assumed that any given particle P in the deformation zone travels on such streamlines and the proportionality relation $\frac{OB}{OA} = \frac{O'B'}{O'A'}$ holds along the

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entire trajectory. It can thus be seen that this assumption presents a method to mathematically define the deformation zone in the shape rolling of an arbitrary section to another arbitrary section [17]. Bezier's parametric curve formulation has been used to describe the streamlines [18].

Bezier used Bernstein polynomials as blending functions for his vectors. He also suggested the use of control points, where a curve of degree n has n control points $V_i (i = 0,1,2,3,\dots,n)$. The Bezier curve passes only through the first and final control points and approximates towards the intermediate points. This research uses cubic Bezier curves.

As illustrated in Fig. 2, the curve so formulated passes through points V_0 and V_3 , and has tangents at V_0 from V_0 to V_1 and at V_3 from V_2 to V_3 . It is also evident from the figure that as one or more control points are moved, the shape of the Bezier curve changes accordingly.

Figure 2 – A typical Bezier curve of degree 3 passes through V_0 and V_3 and has tangents at V_0 from V_0 to V_1 and at V_3 from V_2 to V_3

Bezier's curve of degree 3 is defined as

$$\vec{r}(t) = (1-t)^3 \vec{V}_0 + 3t(1-t)^2 \vec{V}_1 + 3t^2(1-t) \vec{V}_2 + t^3 \vec{V}_3 \quad (1)$$

Or in matrix formation

$$\vec{r}(t) = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & t & t^2 & t^3 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ -3 & 3 & -2 & -1 \\ 2 & -2 & 1 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \vec{V}_0 \\ \vec{V}_1 \\ \vec{V}_2 \\ \vec{V}_3 \end{bmatrix} \quad (2)$$

Where \vec{V}_0 through \vec{V}_3 mark the position vectors of the control points, $0 \leq t \leq 1$ is the main curve defining parameter and $\vec{r}(t)$ is the position vector of a given point on the curve.

To express streamlines within the deformation zone as Bezier curves requires that $\vec{V}_0, \vec{V}_1, \vec{V}_2$ and \vec{V}_3 be appropriately defined. In the present paper, the following general format has been chosen for the vectors.

$$\begin{aligned} \vec{V}_0 &= F_0(u, q)\vec{i} + G_0(u, q)\vec{j} \\ \vec{V}_1 &= a_1 F_0(u, q)\vec{i} + b_1 G_0(u, q)\vec{j} + c_1 H_0(u, q)\vec{k} \\ \vec{V}_2 &= a_2 F_1(u, q)\vec{i} + b_2 G_1(u, q)\vec{j} + c_2 H_1(u, q)\vec{k} \\ \vec{V}_3 &= F_1(u, q)\vec{i} + G_1(u, q)\vec{j} + H_1(u, q)\vec{k} \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

Where F_0 and G_0 are functions that determine the location of point B (Fig. 1) and its position vector \vec{V}_0 , F_1 and G_1 the location of B' and position vector \vec{V}_3 , H_0 and H_1 the position of the tangent vectors. a_1, a_2, b_1, b_2, c_1 and c_2 are arbitrary coefficients that help determine the position of control points. As depicted in Fig. 2, \vec{V}_0 and \vec{V}_3 are the position vectors of points B and B' respectively; \vec{V}_1 and \vec{V}_2 are the tangent vectors at these points. F_0 through H_1 have been assumed as functions of two other parameters u and q where $0 \leq u, q \leq 1$.

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Combining equations 1 and 3:

$$\vec{r} = f(u, q, t)\vec{i} + g(u, q, t)\vec{j} + h(u, q, t)\vec{k} \quad (4)$$

And in the Cartesian coordinate system:

$$\begin{aligned} x &= f(u, q, t) \\ y &= g(u, q, t) \\ z &= h(u, q, t) \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

The total power W required to deform the material in a rolling operation is expressed as the sum of the following components: the power required to deform the material plastically, W_i ; the power required to overcome shear forces resulting from velocity discontinuities at entry, W_e ; and exit, W_x ; and the power required to overcome friction, W_f . In mathematical terms:

$$W = W_i + W_e + W_x + W_f \quad (6)$$

Where

$$\begin{aligned} W_i &= \frac{2\bar{\sigma}}{\sqrt{3}} \int_V (\dot{\epsilon}_{ij} \cdot \dot{\epsilon}_{ij})^{1/2} dV \\ W_e &= \frac{\bar{\sigma}}{\sqrt{3}} \int_{A_1} V_1 \cdot dA_1 \\ W_x &= \frac{\bar{\sigma}}{\sqrt{3}} \int_{A_2} V_2 \cdot dA_2 \\ W_f &= \frac{m \cdot \bar{\sigma}}{\sqrt{3}} \int_{A_f} V_f \cdot dA_f \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

Assuming the deforming material flows according to the Levy-Mises rule and obeys the Mises yield criteria [17], incompressibility condition in three dimensional metal flows can be expressed as follows:

$$\frac{\partial V_x}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial V_y}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial V_z}{\partial z} = 0 \quad (8)$$

V_x , V_y and V_z are the components of the three dimensional velocity vector along coordinate axes X , Y and Z respectively. Equating the unit tangent vector for the point P on the streamline BB' (Fig. 1) to the unit velocity vector yields:

$$\begin{aligned} V_x &= \frac{f_t}{h_t} V_z \\ V_y &= \frac{g_t}{h_t} V_z \\ V_z &= M(u, q, t) \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

A kinematically admissible velocity field must essentially satisfy the incompressibility condition. Substituting V_x , V_y and V_z from (9) into (8) and solving for $M(u, q, t)$:

$$M = \frac{C \cdot h_t}{h_t(f_u g_q - f_q g_u) + h_q(f_t g_u - f_u g_t) + h_u(f_q g_t - f_t g_q)} \quad (10)$$

Where C is a constant to be determined from the specific velocity boundary conditions of each section studied. Velocities calculated using (10) automatically satisfy the incompressibility or the volume constancy condition.

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Using the parametric notation employed in this study, the plastic deformation component of the total rolling power may be expressed as follows:

$$W_i = \frac{2\bar{\sigma}}{\sqrt{3}} \int_V \left(\frac{\dot{\epsilon}_{xx}^2 + \dot{\epsilon}_{yy}^2 + \dot{\epsilon}_{zz}^2}{2} + \dot{\epsilon}_{xy}^2 + \dot{\epsilon}_{yz}^2 + \dot{\epsilon}_{zx}^2 \right)^{1/2} |J| \cdot dudqdt \quad (11)$$

$\dot{\epsilon}_{xx} \dots$ are strain rates in various directions, $\bar{\sigma}$ is the flow stress and $|J|$ is the Jacobian for transformation of coordinates from x, y, z to u, q, t .

The velocity discontinuity components of total rolling power can be expressed as follows. At entry:

$$W_e = \frac{\bar{\sigma}}{\sqrt{3}} \int_0^1 \int_0^1 (V_x^2 + V_y^2)^{1/2} \frac{\partial(x, y)}{\partial(u, q)} \Big|_{t=0} dudq \quad (12)$$

At exit:

$$W_x = \frac{\bar{\sigma}}{\sqrt{3}} \int_0^1 \int_0^1 (V_x^2 + V_y^2)^{1/2} \frac{\partial(x, y)}{\partial(u, q)} \Big|_{t=1} dudq \quad (13)$$

The friction component:

$$W_f = \frac{m\bar{\sigma}}{\sqrt{3}} \int_0^1 \int_0^1 \sqrt{(V_t - V_r)^2 + V_y^2} \Big|_{u=1} \cdot \sec \alpha \cdot \frac{\partial(x, z)}{\partial(q, t)} \Big|_{u=1} \cdot dq \cdot dt \quad (14)$$

Where

$$\sec \alpha = \frac{\sqrt{(N_1^2 + N_2^2 + N_3^2)}}{N_2} \quad \text{and} \quad \vec{N} = \frac{\partial \vec{r}}{\partial q} \Big|_{u=1} \times \frac{\partial \vec{r}}{\partial t} \Big|_{u=1}, \quad V_t = \sqrt{V_x^2 + V_z^2} \quad \text{and} \quad V_r \quad \text{is the}$$

tangential roll velocity.

Simulation of pass sequences

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The analytical model presented earlier has been employed to simulate specific passes in shape rolling as follows.

A – Square to Oval pass

Figure 3 shows the three dimensional deformation zone for the rolling of a square billet to an oval bar. Lower roll has been omitted for clarity. As the rolling geometry is assumed to be symmetrical, a quarter of the deformation zone suffices for the purpose of this analysis. Figure 4 depicts a quarter of the deformation zone for the square to oval pass.

Figure 3 – Three dimensional deformation zone the for square to oval shape rolling (lower roll omitted for clarity)

Figure 4 – A quarter of the deformation zone for square to oval pass (depicted in sections for clarity)

It has been assumed that solid grooved rolls draw the billet inside the roll gap and reduce its cross section (Fig. 3). The projected length of the deformation zone z_0 (Fig. 4) is calculated using the geometrical specifics of the pass and billet dimensions.

The analysis requires an analytical representation of the three dimensional roll groove surface. Assuming that the curve defining the exit cross section of the rolls has been defined as $y = f(x)$; every point on the roll groove surface is generated by the rotation of a corresponding point on the curve about the upper roll axis $y = y_c$. The three dimensional roll groove surface may thus be expressed as:

$$(y_c - f(x))^2 = (y - y_c)^2 + (z_0 - z)^2 \quad (15)$$

y and z are the coordinates of a rotated point on the roll groove surface.

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The entry cross section for the square to oval pass has been assumed to be a square with sides $2s$ in length and the exit cross section an oval with a major axis of length $2a$ and a minor axis of length $2b$.

Considering the complexity of the deformation zone and the approximate metal flow in the square-oval pass, it was decided for the purpose of this study that a single Bezier curve will be insufficient to describe the entire deformation zone. To facilitate the analysis, the following assumptions have been made.

- That the deformation zone consists of three smaller zones; the zone bound between the plane $OBB'O'$ and the surface $OAB'O'$, the zone limited to $OAB'O'$ and the surface $OAA'O'$, and the zone lying between $OAA'O'$ and the surface CAC' , as shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5 – Zoning of the deformation zone in square-oval pass. Typical streamlines have been depicted as QQ'' and SS' .

- That a particle entering the deformation zone from within the perimeter of triangle OAB travels along its assigned streamline, e.g. QQ' , which lies somewhere between $OBB'O'$ and $OAB'O'$ until it reaches $OAB'O'$, where a second streamline, e.g. $Q'Q''$, originates. The particle then resumes its course along the latter which lies between $OAB'O'$ and the plane $OAA'O'$ (see Fig. 5).

- That particles entering the deformation zone from within the perimeter of triangle OAC travel along designated streamlines, e.g. SS' , without encountering a second surface to exit the deformation zone from the area bound by $O'A'$ and $O'C'$ (see Fig. 5).

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- That the deformation zone can be aptly described by the three typical streamlines mentioned; QQ' , $Q'Q''$ describe the first half and SS' describes the second half (see Fig. 5).

The parametric Bezier formulation for the first streamline, e.g. QQ' , may be expressed as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \vec{V}_0 &= ustg\varphi \cdot \vec{i} + us \cdot \vec{j} \\
 \vec{V}_1 &= a_1ustg\varphi \cdot \vec{i} + b_1us \cdot \vec{j} + c_1z_0 \cdot \vec{k} \\
 \vec{V}_2 &= a_2ustg\varphi \cdot \vec{i} + b_2u(y_c - \sqrt{(y_c - \frac{b}{a}\sqrt{a^2 - s^2tg^2\varphi})^2 - z_0^2tg^2\varphi}) \cdot \vec{j} + c_2(z_0 - z_0utg\varphi) \cdot \vec{k} \\
 \vec{V}_3 &= ustg\varphi \cdot \vec{i} + u(y_c - \sqrt{(y_c - \frac{b}{a}\sqrt{a^2 - s^2tg^2\varphi})^2 - z_0^2tg^2\varphi}) \cdot \vec{j} + (z_0 - z_0utg\varphi) \cdot \vec{k}
 \end{aligned}$$

(16)

Where $\phi = \frac{\pi q}{4}$ describes the angular position of the first control point \vec{V}_0 and the curve may be expressed in parametric terms as

$$\vec{r}(u, q, t) = (1-t)^3\vec{V}_0 + 3t(1-t^2)\vec{V}_1 + 3t^2(1-t)\vec{V}_2 + t^3\vec{V}_3 \quad (17)$$

Or in Cartesian form

$$\vec{r}(u, q, t) = f(u, q, t)\vec{i} + g(u, q, t)\vec{j} + h(u, q, t)\vec{k} \quad (18)$$

The Bezier formulation for the second streamline, e.g. $Q'Q''$, may be expressed as follows

$$\begin{aligned}
 \vec{V}'_0 &= ustg\varphi \cdot \vec{i} + u(y_c - \sqrt{(y_c - \frac{b}{a}\sqrt{a^2 - s^2 tg^2 \varphi})^2 - z_0^2 tg^2 \varphi}) \cdot \vec{j} + (z_0 - z_0 utg\varphi) \cdot \vec{k} \\
 \vec{V}'_1 &= [1 + k_1(1 - a_2)]ustg\varphi \cdot \vec{i} + [(1 + k_1(1 - b_2))u(y_c - \sqrt{(y_c - \frac{b}{a}\sqrt{a^2 - s^2 tg^2 \varphi})^2 - z_0^2 tg^2 \varphi}) \cdot \vec{j} + \\
 &[(1 + k_1(1 - c_2))(z_0 - z_0 utg\varphi) \cdot \vec{k} \\
 \vec{V}'_2 &= [2k_1(1 - a_2) + k_2(1 - 2a_2) + k_2 a_1]ustg\varphi \cdot \vec{i} + \\
 &\left[[2k_1(1 - b_2) + k_2(1 - 2b_2) + 1]u(y_c - \sqrt{(y_c - \frac{b}{a}\sqrt{a^2 - s^2 tg^2 \varphi})^2 - z_0^2 tg^2 \varphi}) + k_2 b_1 us \right] \cdot \vec{j} + \\
 &\left[[2k_1(1 - c_2) + k_2(1 - 2c_2) + 1](z_0 - z_0 utg\varphi) + k_2 c_1 z_0 \right] \cdot \vec{k} \\
 \vec{V}'_3 &= u(am) \cdot \vec{i} + u(b\sqrt{1 - m^2}) \cdot \vec{j} + z_0 \cdot \vec{k}
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{19}$$

Where $m = \sin(\frac{\pi}{4}tg\varphi)$ and k_1 and k_2 are additional parameters introduced to maintain slope and curvature at the junction of the two streamlines, e.g. QQ' and $Q'Q''$. (18) and (19) ensure that there is no velocity discontinuity at the junction point.

The second curve may be expressed in parametric terms as follows

$$\vec{r}'(u, q, t) = (1 - t)^3 \vec{V}'_0 + 3t(1 - t^2) \vec{V}'_1 + 3t^2(1 - t) \vec{V}'_2 + t^3 \vec{V}'_3 \tag{20}$$

Or in Cartesian coordinates

$$\vec{r}'(u, q, t) = f'(u, q, t) \vec{i} + g'(u, q, t) \vec{j} + h'(u, q, t) \vec{k} \tag{21}$$

Streamlines in the second half of the deformation zone, e.g. SS' , may be described in parametric Bezier formulation as follows

$$\begin{aligned}
 \vec{V}''_0 &= us \cdot \vec{i} + ustg\varphi \cdot \vec{j} \\
 \vec{V}''_1 &= a'_1 us \cdot \vec{i} + b'_1 ustg\varphi \cdot \vec{j} + c'_1 z_0 \cdot \vec{k} \\
 \vec{V}''_2 &= a'_2 u(a\sqrt{1 - m^2}) \cdot \vec{i} + b'_2 u(bm) \cdot \vec{j} + c'_2 z_0 \cdot \vec{k} \\
 \vec{V}''_3 &= u(a\sqrt{1 - m^2}) \cdot \vec{i} + u(bm) \cdot \vec{j} + z_0 \cdot \vec{k}
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{22}$$

In parametric terms

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$$\vec{r}''(u, q, t) = (1-t)^3 \vec{V}_0'' + 3t(1-t^2) \vec{V}_1'' + 3t^2(1-t) \vec{V}_2'' + t^3 \vec{V}_3'' \quad (23)$$

And in Cartesian coordinates

$$\vec{r}''(u, q, t) = f''(u, q, t) \vec{i} + g''(u, q, t) \vec{j} + h''(u, q, t) \vec{k} \quad (24)$$

The sum of \vec{r} , \vec{r}' and \vec{r}'' provides a parametric definition of all the streamlines in the deformation zone. The summation includes 14 unknown coefficients; a_1 to c_2 , a'_1 to c'_2 , k_1 and k_2 which will be determined through optimization of the total power required. The relations developed so far satisfy both the incompressibility and velocity continuity conditions. To ensure that velocity boundary conditions are met, a subsidiary constraint was imposed; streamlines located on the roll-workpiece interface must also be located on the roll surface. In mathematical terms, this translates into the condition that where $u = 1$, the parametric expression of the curve must satisfy the three dimensional roll surface equation (15).

A second constraint was imposed to preclude velocity discontinuities between streamlines located on the boundary between the two halves of the entry cross section. In mathematical terms, this means that where $q = 1$, $\vec{r}(u, q, t) = \vec{r}''(u, q, t)_{q=1}$.

A MATLAB computer code utilizing the Genetic Algorithm was generated to perform the optimization. Using Simpson's Three Point Rule, W_i was calculated by numerical integration with respect to each of the parameters u , q and t . For W_e and W_x analytical integration with respect to u was followed by numerical integration with respect to q using a three-point Simpson Rule. For W_f , integration was performed numerically with respect to both parameters using the five point rule.

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B – Round to Oval Pass

Figures 6 and 7 show respectively the entire deformation zone and a quarter of the typical deformation zone in the round to oval pass.

Figure 6 – Three dimensional deformation zone the for round to oval shape rolling (lower roll omitted for clarity)

Figure 7 – A quarter of the deformation zone for round to oval pass (depicted in sections for clarity)

For the round to oval pass, it has been assumed that the entry cross section is a circle of radius r and the exit section an oval with a major axis of length $2a$ and a minor axis of length $2b$ (Fig. 7).

Due to the relatively less complex metal flow patterns in round to oval rolling as compared to the square to oval rolling sequence, a single Bezier curve was found sufficient to describe the entire deformation zone. The Bezier control points have been found as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \vec{V}_0 &= ur \sin \varphi \cdot \vec{i} + ur \cos \varphi \cdot \vec{j} \\
 \vec{V}_1 &= a_1 ur \sin \varphi \cdot \vec{i} + b_1 ur \cos \varphi \cdot \vec{j} + c_1 z_0 \cdot \vec{k} \\
 \vec{V}_2 &= a_2 ua \sin \varphi \cdot \vec{i} + b_2 ub \cos \varphi \cdot \vec{j} + c_2 z_0 \cdot \vec{k} \\
 \vec{V}_3 &= ua \sin \varphi \cdot \vec{i} + ub \cos \varphi \cdot \vec{j} + z_0 \cdot \vec{k}
 \end{aligned} \tag{25}$$

Where $\varphi = \frac{\pi q}{2}$ and the curve itself in parametric terms

$$\vec{r}(u, q, t) = (1-t)^3 \vec{V}_0 + 3t(1-t)^2 \vec{V}_1 + 3t^2(1-t) \vec{V}_2 + t^3 \vec{V}_3$$

And in Cartesian coordinates

$$\vec{r}(u, q, t) = f(u, q, t) \vec{i} + g(u, q, t) \vec{j} + h(u, q, t) \vec{k}$$

Velocities in the three coordinate directions may be expressed as

$$M = \frac{\pi V_e r^2 u}{2[(f_q g_u - f_u g_q) - \frac{h_q}{h_t}(f_t g_u - f_u g_t) - \frac{h_u}{h_t}(f_q g_t - f_t g_q)]}$$

$$V_x = \frac{f_t}{h_t} V_z \quad (26)$$

$$V_y = \frac{g_t}{h_t} V_z$$

The velocities derived satisfy both the incompressibility and the velocity continuity conditions. To ensure that velocity boundary conditions are met, the first subsidiary constraint mentioned earlier was imposed.

Results

The analysis above was applied to square to oval and oval to round rolling operations for which other results were available from experiments or analyses discussed in the literature. Comparisons were made between those results and the results acquired from the present study.

A – Square to Oval

The square to oval pass was evaluated against the experiment/analysis carried out in [14]. Table 1 outlines the analytical conditions for the square to oval pass.

The material is low carbon steel – AISI 1018 – and rolling was performed at 1090° at which temperature the flow stress may be described by [14]

$$\bar{\sigma} = 77.5 \dot{\epsilon}^{0.192} MPa \quad (27)$$

Figures 8 to 12 illustrate the process of rolling various cross sections within the deformation zone, from $\frac{z}{z_0} = 0$ to $\frac{z}{z_0} = 1$, as predicted by the present method. In each figure, the cross sectional shape predicted by [14] has been superimposed.

Figure 8 – Predicted cross section at $\frac{z}{z_0} = 0$ (entry) for square to oval pass (Reference [14] superimposed in dashed lines)

Figure 9 – Predicted cross section at $\frac{z}{z_0} = 0.25$ for square to oval pass

Figure 10 – Predicted cross section at $\frac{z}{z_0} = 0.5$ for square to oval pass

Figure 11 – Predicted cross section at $\frac{z}{z_0} = 0.75$ for square to oval pass

Figure 12 – Predicted cross section at $\frac{z}{z_0} = 1$ (exit) for square to oval pass

It can be observed from Figures 8 to 12 that in all cases the present study predicts a cross section closer to the actual roll surface than reference [14]. Due to the streamline formulation, the present analysis predicts a curved, continuous side while reference [14] predicts a flat side. For the three middle sections, figures 9 to 11, the present study predicts a slight discontinuity, the location of which has been denoted by a straight line. This discontinuity is due to the inevitable approximation when applying the second constraint mentioned earlier.

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Roll torque has been calculated by varying roll pass dimensions to incorporate several

area reduction values ($q = 1 - \frac{A_{ex}}{A_e}$) and by applying different frictional conditions;

$m = 0.2, 0.4, 0.6, 0.75$. The effect of friction on roll torque was investigated in figure 13.

The same area reduction and friction factor values have been used to calculate the ratio of the average roll pressure to flow stress as shown in figure 14.

Figure 13 – Square to oval roll torque calculated for various reduction and friction factor values

Figure 14 – The ratio of average roll pressure to flow stress calculated for various reduction and friction factor values

It can be seen from figures 13 and 14 that both the roll torque and the ratio of the average roll pressure to flow stress increase with an increase in reduction and friction factor, in effect requiring greater rolling power. Friction factor directly affects the power required to overcome friction forces and thus the total rolling power. The effect of reduction is less explicit, influencing both entry and exit cross section dimensions, velocity fields and all of the rolling power components.

B – Round to Oval pass

The round to oval analysis was evaluated against the experiments conducted in [1] and the flowline field solution attempted in [12]. The experiments carried out in [1] include a round-oval-round four pass sequence in which the material, temperature and flow stress data are the same as in part A. Pass data for the round to oval passes analyzed in this study are outlined in Table 2. Tables 3 and 4 show results for average roll pressure and

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exit velocity from the present analysis, the flowline field solution [12], and experiment [1].

In both cases, the present upper bound method predicts the average roll pressure and exit velocity with acceptable accuracy, although the amounts predicted here are higher than the flowline field solution predictions.

Summary and conclusions

A method has been proposed to analyze metal deformation, roll torque, average roll pressure and exit velocity for the rolling of simple geometrical shapes. The method employs the upper bound solution in which numerical methods have been used to optimize the total power required to deform the material and in the process unknown variables have been determined. The upper bound method was based on a new application of parametric curve formulation to define streamlines within the deformation zone. The formulation used simplifying assumptions to enable analysis of the fairly complex metal flow in the rolling operations discussed. Based upon the parametric formulation, a kinematically admissible velocity field was derived and based on the velocity fields, upper bounds were established for the power.

Based on the comparison made between the results obtained from this analysis and experimental/analytical studies by other authors, the following conclusions have been made:

- The shape rolling analysis presented is capable of accurately predicting metal flow patterns, although the sides are curved.

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- The shape rolling analysis presented is capable of accurately predicting roll torque and average roll pressure. However, due to the nature of the upper bound method, the analysis predicts slightly higher values.

- For sections in which the deforming material initiates contact with the roll groove surface toward the outer edge of the entry cross section, such as the square to oval pass, additional parameters are required to allow an accurate representation of the deformation zone in comparison with sections in which initial contact happens toward the inner edges of the entry cross section, such as the round to oval pass. In the former case, the additional surfaces and curves complicate the analysis and slow convergence to optimum. As a result, the upper bound analysis is less accurate than that for the sections which initiate contact toward the inner edges.

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